

Influence of carbon doping on stability of intrinsic defects in $\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$

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Abstract

Methods of crystal growth of rare earth garnets without precious metal crucibles are extensively developed nowadays. This work addresses defects forming in carbon-containing $\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ crystals grown in Ar+CO atmosphere in W crucibles. Influence of carbon admixture on formation energies and oxidation states of intrinsic defects has been studied by ab-initio calculations and optical spectroscopy. Twenty-one type of isolated and complex defects have been considered in oxygen-poor conditions of crystal growth in Ar+CO reducing atmosphere and oxygen-rich conditions of post-growth annealing of crystals in air. Despite the same type of crystalline structure and similar chemical compositions of $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ and $\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$, the remarkable differences in formation mechanisms of color centers have been found in these materials.

Keywords: Lutetium aluminum garnet; ab-initio calculations; carbon doping; defects

1. Introduction

Rare earth garnets remain a one of major directions of scintillation material research due to their flexibility in terms of cationic composition and possibility of fine tuning their optical and scintillation parameters. Methods of garnet crystal growth have been also extensively developed, because traditional methods of growth from melt involve Ir crucibles, which cost has increased dramatically during last decade. Among the recent developments, one may note the growth of $\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ (LuAG:Ce) from Mo crucibles by EFG in reducing atmosphere [1], attempts to crystallize $\text{Gd}_3\text{Al}_{5-x}\text{Ga}_x\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce}$ (GAGG:Ce) by the cold crucible method in oxidizing atmosphere [2]. In the meantime, a method of garnet growth in W/Mo crucibles has been developed in ISMA (Kharkiv, Ukraine) [3], which employs CO reducing atmosphere instead of Ar/H₂ mixture mainly used at growth without precious metal crucibles. Meanwhile, additional questions rise regarding the contamination of melts and crystals with crucible materials (W, Mo) or gas constituents. This aspect is of importance for crystals grown in CO-containing atmosphere, because up to 0.6 at% of carbon was detected in $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ (YAG) by carrier hot gas extraction method [4]. This concentration exceeds the amount of any intrinsic defects in rare earth garnets.

In our recent works, we evaluated the possibilities of carbon incorporation into different crystallographic positions and interstitials, as well as the formation of complex carbon-containing defects in Ce-free (YAG:C) [5] and Ce-doped (YAG:Ce,C) yttrium aluminum garnet [6]. It was determined that the most stable defects are positively charged in crystals grown in oxygen-poor environment of Ar+CO, creating conditions for electron capture and formation of color centers. Meanwhile, negatively charged defects were the most stable in the simulation in oxygen-rich conditions, corresponding to the annealing in air. These results complemented our optical data [7] indicating a huge number of color centers in as-grown crystals, but their very low concentration in crystals annealed in oxidizing conditions. Meanwhile, light yield dramatically increased in annealed YAG:Ce up to ca. 30000 ph/MeV that pushed us to the conclusion that carbon-doping may promote stabilization of Ce in the trivalent state and enhance electron

transport to Ce activator centers [4]. Recently [8], similar enhancement of scintillation parameters was reported for $\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce,C}$ (LuAG:Ce,C) and $\text{Lu}_{3-x}\text{Y}_x\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}:\text{Ce,C}$ (LuYAG:Ce,C) where a high light yield up to 28000 ph/MeV, and no color centers were identified in air-annealed crystals.

In this work, by the same methodology [5, 6] we evaluated the formation energies and oxidation states of intrinsic and carbon-induced defects, as well as optical absorption spectra of LuAG:C crystals grown under reducing CO-containing atmosphere in W crucibles and annealed in air.

2. Experimental

2.1. Theoretical method

$\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ possesses a cubic structure being identical to $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ [9]. The lattice constant is calculated to be 11.87 Å, which agrees well with the experimental value of 11.91 Å [10]. By the analogy to the study on YAG:C [5], 21 types of possible isolated and complex defects were considered (Table 1). We did not consider carbon or aluminum occupying Lu sites, as well as Lu vacancies, because, according to the element analysis of YAG crystals grown under CO-containing atmosphere, crystal surface is severely depleted with aluminum and oxygen [11] that also should affect crystal bulk.

Table 1. Defects in LuAG lattice considered in the calculations.

Types of defects		
Isolated defects	intrinsic	V_{O} (oxygen vacancy), $V_{\text{Al-4}}$, $V_{\text{Al-6}}$ (vacancy of 4-coordinated or 6-coordinated Al^{3+}), $\text{Lu}_{\text{Al-4}}$, $\text{Lu}_{\text{Al-6}}$ (Lu occupying 4- or 6-coordinated Al^{3+} sites (“antisites”))

Isolated carbon-related defects	C_{Al-4} , C_{Al-6} (carbon occupying 4- or 6-coordinated Al^{3+} sites) C_O (carbon occupying oxygen sites) C_i (interstitial carbon)
Complex defects (combinations of isolated defects)	C_{Al-4-V_O} , C_{Al-6-V_O} , C_O-V_O , C_i-V_O C_O-Lu_{Al-4} , C_i-Lu_{Al-4} , C_O-Lu_{Al-6} , C_i-Lu_{Al-6} C_O-V_{Al-4} , C_i-V_{Al-4} , C_O-V_{Al-6} , C_i-V_{Al-6}

The defect formation energy calculations were carried out in the framework of density functional theory and the projector augmented wave method, as implemented in Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package [12]. The generalized gradient approximation proposed by Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof was selected for exchange-correlation potential [13]. The plane-wave cut-off energy was set to be 400 eV. The total energy converged to 10^{-6} eV in the iterative solution of Kohn-Sham equation. The Brillouin zone integration was performed in $2 \times 2 \times 2$ k-mesh. All structures were relaxed until the residual forces on the atoms are less than 0.01 eV/Å. The calculations were performed in the unit cell containing 160 atoms. The deviation of formation energy for charged defects was only 0.2 eV in the supercell containing 320 atoms.

The formation energy of defects are defined as [14]

$$\Delta H(D, q) = E(D, q) - E(\text{perfect}) + \sum n_i \mu_i + q(E_{VBM} + E_F),$$

where $E(D, q)$ is the total energy of the system with defect D in charge state q , n_i and μ_i refer to the number and chemical potential of atom i , and E_{VBM} and E_F represent the energy of the valence band maximum and the Fermi level. The band gap of $Lu_3Al_5O_{12}$ is measured to be 8.2 eV [15]. The chemical potentials of the Lu, Al, O, and C atoms are subject to

$$3\mu_{Lu} + 5\mu_{Al} + 12\mu_O = E(Lu_3Al_5O_{12})$$

$$2\mu_{Lu} + 3\mu_O \leq E(Lu_2O_3)$$

$$2\mu_{Al} + 3\mu_O \leq E(Al_2O_3)$$

$$\mu_C + \mu_O = E(\text{CO})$$

$$\mu_M \leq E(M),$$

where M represents Lu, Al, O, and C.

2.2. Crystal growth and characterization

YAG and LuAG crystals were grown by the Czochralski method in W crucibles under Ar+CO atmosphere (the growth procedure is described elsewhere [3]). The samples for optical measurements were cut from crack-free parts of the boules in the shape of 5x5x1 mm plates with the 5x5 polished faces. The absorption spectra in UV-VIS regions were recorded by SPECORD 40 (Analytic Jena) spectrophotometer before and after annealing the samples in air at 1200 °C during 12 hours. Photoluminescence (PL) emission spectra in the 200–800 nm range were determined using a combined fluorescent lifetime and steady-state spectrometer FLS 920 (Edinburgh Instruments) equipped with a Xe 450 W lamp for steady-state measurements. Emission spectra were corrected for the spectral sensitivity of the detection system.

3. Results

3.1. Ab initio calculations

Figure 1 shows the stable window of atomic potentials of Lu and Al in $\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ subject to the byproducts. The O chemical potential reaches the maximal value (-4.94 eV) at the points A and B referring to Lu_2O_3 excess and Al_2O_3 excess. The corresponding Lu/Al chemical potentials are -13.79/-11.48 eV and -14.03/-11.34 eV, respectively. On the other hand, the Lu/Al chemical potentials are calculated to be -6.44/-3.75 eV and -6.06/-3.75 eV at the points C and D. The corresponding O chemical potentials show to be -9.99 eV and -10.08 eV. The points A and D are thus selected as the O-rich and O-poor limits in calculation of the defect formation energies.

Figure 1 Stable window of atomic chemical potential of Lu, Al, and O in $\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$. The points A and D are selected for the following calculations.

3.1.1. Formation energies and oxidation states of LuAG intrinsic defects

The formation energies of intrinsic defects, namely Lu substitution at 4-fold and 6-fold coordinated Al site ($\text{Lu}_{\text{Al-4}}$ and $\text{Lu}_{\text{Al-6}}$) named as antisite defects, Al vacancies ($V_{\text{Al-4}}$ and $V_{\text{Al-6}}$), and O vacancies (V_{O}), at O-rich and O-poor limits are illustrated in Figure 2. Positively charged V_{O} and negatively charged aluminum vacancies are the most stable intrinsic defects in as-grown crystals (oxygen-poor conditions). The V_{O} shows lower formation energies than $V_{\text{Al-4}}$ for the Fermi level below 1.02 and 4.21 eV for O-rich and O-poor limits, respectively. Expectedly, the probability oxygen vacancy formation decreases in oxygen-rich conditions. The formation energies of $\text{Lu}_{\text{Al-4}}$ and $\text{Lu}_{\text{Al-6}}$ are not influenced by the atomic chemical potentials because of their stoichiometric nature, thus the $\text{Lu}_{\text{Al-4}}$ and $\text{Lu}_{\text{Al-6}}$ remain neutral and not affected by the location of the Fermi level. Stability of the intrinsic defects in $\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ revealed in this work is similar to that reported in $\text{Y}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ [5]. The V_{O} introduces a thermodynamic transition level $\epsilon(+2/0)$ at 2.79

eV above the valence band maximum. The charge states of V_{Al-4} turn out to be 0, +1, +2, and +3 for the Fermi level lies above 0.00, 0.46, 0.65, and 0.86 eV.

Figure 2 Formation energies of intrinsic defects, including Lu substitution at 4-fold and 6-fold coordinated Al site (Lu_{Al-4} and Lu_{Al-6}), Al vacancies (V_{Al-4} and V_{Al-6}), and O vacancies (V_O), as a function of the Fermi level under O-rich and O-poor limits. The charge states of the defects are represented by the slopes of the segments.

3.1.2. Formation energies and oxidation states of isolated carbon-related defects in LuAG:C.

C prefers to occupy the 4-fold coordinated Al site (C_{Al-4}), followed by the 6-fold coordinated Al site (C_{Al-6}) for the O-rich limit (Figure 3). The interstitial (C_i) sites are not favorable, by the analogy to YAG:C, while the formation energy C_O is close to zero. The C_O site is preferred in the O-poor limit for the Fermi level below 6.48 eV, whereas the C in Al sites is more stable for higher Fermi level energies in both atmosphere conditions. However, C_O defects are neutral, unlike the case of YAG:C where such defects are positively charged in oxygen-poor conditions with the formation energies of up to 9 eV [5]. The C_{Al-4} demonstrates 0 and -3 charge states with a transition level at 5.08 eV above the valence band maximum. The C_{Al-6} also exists in -1 charge state when the Fermi level ranges from 1.83 eV to 4.82 eV. The C_i remains neutral, which is different from the results on YAG:C [5].

Figure 3 Formation energies of C defects, including the 4-fold (C_{Al-4}) and 6-fold (C_{Al-6}) coordinated Al site, O site (C_O), and interstitial (C_i) sites, as a function of the Fermi level under O-rich and O-poor limits. The charge states of the defects are represented by the slopes of the segments.

3.1.3. Formation energies and oxidation states of complex carbon-related defects in LuAG:C

Figure 4 illustrates influence of C doping on stability of Lu substitution at the Al sites (antisite defects). Positively charged antisites near carbon occupying oxygen site (C_O-Lu_{Al}) and negatively charged antisites near C_i interstitials (C_i-Lu_{Al}) are the most favorable defects in as grown crystals grown under oxygen-poor conditions. C_O-Lu_{Al-4} and C_O-Lu_{Al-6} possess +4, +2, +1, and 0 charge states, while C_i-Lu_{Al-4} and C_i-Lu_{Al-6} are stable in +2, +1, 0, and -2 charge states, which is similar to the results on YAG:C [5]. Note that only the isolated antisite defects are stable in neutral charge state in LuAG:C, demonstrating strong interaction in the complex defects. Meanwhile, formation of all the mentioned antisite-related defects is not favorable in the O-rich limit (after the annealing) as the formation energies are positive. The situation is quite similar to YAG:C [5].

Figure 4 Formation energies of complex defects, including the C defects and the Lu substitution at 4-fold (C_O-C_{Al-4} and C_i-C_{Al-4}) and 6-fold (C_O-C_{Al-6} and C_i-C_{Al-6}) coordinated Al site, as a function of the Fermi level under O-rich and O-poor limits. The charge states of the defects are represented by the slopes of the segments.

Figure 5 shows the formation energies of complex C-related defects involving the 4-fold and 6-fold coordinated Al vacancies. The Al vacancies are more stable at low Fermi level energies by introduction of C for the O-poor limit, especially in the case of nearby carbon occupying oxygen sites. The C_O-V_{Al-4} creates transition levels $\epsilon(+3/+)$ and $\epsilon(+/-3)$ at 3.16 eV and 3.66 eV above the valence band maximum, respectively. The transition levels of $\epsilon(+2/+)$, $\epsilon(+/-2)$, $\epsilon(-2/-3)$, and $\epsilon(-3/-4)$ are located at 0.91, 1.22, 4.74, and 5.67 eV for C_i-V_{Al-4} . Meanwhile, V_{Al-4} and V_{Al-6} are largely eliminated by C doping for the Fermi level above 1.95 eV in the O-rich limit, very similar to the case of YAG:C [5].

Figure 5 Formation energies of complex defects, including the C defects and the 4-fold ($C_{O^-}V_{Al-4}$ and $C_{i^-}V_{Al-4}$) and 6-fold ($C_{O^-}V_{Al-6}$ and $C_{i^-}V_{Al-6}$) coordinated Al vacancies, as a function of the Fermi level under O-rich and O-poor limits. The charge states of the defects are represented by the slopes of the segments.

The formation energies of complex defects involving oxygen vacancies are presented in Fig. 6. Carbon doping largely promotes the formation of positively charged $C_{O^-}V_O$ below the Fermi level energy of 2.5 eV and negatively charged $C_{i^-}V_O$ and $C_{Al^-}V_O$ defects above 2.5 eV in as-grown crystals instead of positively charged V_O . $C_{Al^-}V_O$ remains the most favorable defect for the O-rich limit after the annealing, generally repeating the situation in YAG:C [5]. Although the isolated C_i shows neutral charge state (see Fig. 3), the interaction with nearby V_O leads to quite different charge states as compared to the isolated V_O . $C_{O^-}V_O$ is stable in +4, +2, +1, and 0 charge states as compared to +2 and 0 for the isolated V_O .

Figure 6 Formation energies of complex defects, including the C defects O vacancies ($C_{Al-4}-V_O$, $C_{Al-6}-V_O$, C_O-V_O , and C_i-V_O) as a function of the Fermi level under O-rich and O-poor limits. The charge states of the defects are represented by the slopes of the segments.

3.2. Optical study

The shape of optical absorption spectrum of as-grown LuAG:C is completely different from that in YAG:C despite the same crystalline structure and similarity of chemical composition and energy structure in them. While up to 10 peaks were resolved in our previous work on YAG:C [5]), just three clear absorption peaks around 3.4, and 5.25, and 6 eV are distinguished in LuAG:C (Figure 7). After annealing, the absorption is very similar in YAG:C and LuAG:C – it smoothly increases with the energy without strong distinguished peaks, pointing that transmission loss is basically determined by scattering centres created by inclusions in crystals. For reference, the view of elements produced from as-grown and annealed YAG:C and LuAG crystals are illustrated in Fig. 8. The impact of annealing on optical absorption in YAG:C was addressed by us in detail in [7].

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. Absorption spectra of LuAG (a) and YAG (b) before/after the thermal treatment in air atmosphere at 1200 °C during 12 hours. The peak energies in eV are depicted.

Complementary to the optical absorption data, an intense blue luminescence of defects is observed in as-grown LuAG:C (Fig. 8). Such emission was attributed to F^+ centers in garnets [16]. At the same time, just a weak red luminescence (almost invisible by naked eye) is observed in as-grown crystals under excitation in UV-band. The nature of these long-wavelength bands is still contested. They may be attributed both to Fe^{3+} admixture, or carbon-related defects as was proposed in [4]. A weak luminescence of defects in annealed LuAG:C is an additional evidence

of F^+ -center elimination after annealing in air, related to the decreasing amount of positively charged defects shown in our calculations.

Fig. 8. Luminescence spectra of LuAG:C before (left) and after (right) the annealing in air at 1200 °C during 12 hours. Excitation wavelengths are depicted in the legends.

4. Discussion

In general, the formation energies of complex carbon-related defects are rather similar in YAG:C and LuAG:C, which is not surprising keeping in mind their similar chemical composition and the same type of crystal structure. At crystal growth under oxygen-poor Ar+CO reducing conditions, the lowest formation energies are obtained for the C_O-V_O , C_i-V_O , C_O-LuAl , C_i-LuAl , and C_O-V_{Al} complex defects. Therefore, C_O^- and C_i -containing defects are stabilized by the presence of nearby oxygen vacancies, $LuAl$ antisites, or aluminum vacancies. $C_{Al}-V_O$, C_i-V_{Al} and C_O-V_{Al} defects with the largest formation energies are the most favorable ones after annealing in air, whereas antisites are suppressed with carbon doping, and the complex C_i-V_O and C_O-V_O defects

tend to be destroyed due to filling oxygen vacancies. Having the most energetically favorable negative oxidation states, C_i-V_{Al} and C_O-V_{Al} repulse electrons, suppressing F-type center formation that should promote electron transport to activators, such as Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} . In addition, C_{Al} , $C_{Al}-V_O$ also do not form color centers as under the annealing they switch into the most energetically favorable -2 and -3 oxidation states, respectively (see Figures 3, 6).

The shape of optical absorption spectra indicate a greater diversity of color centers in as-grown YAG:C as compared to LuAG:C. Lower quantity of F-center-related absorption peaks in as-grown LuAG:C may be caused by the absence of color centers related to the discharged isolated C_O and C_i defects. By the analogy with YAG:C, the remaining complex defects in LuAG:C annealed in air are negatively charged and do not form color centers that describes the absence of remarkable F-type absorption bands in the spectrum.

Therefore, the main difference found between the formation energies and oxidation states of carbon-related defects in YAG:C [5] and LuAG:C is the neutrality of C_O and C_i isolated defects in the former. Both these defects possessing positive oxidation states in as-grown YAG:C tend to capture electrons and form color centers. Furthermore, in LuAG:C the formation of C_i defect is not favorable (formation energy is over +5 eV), while it is around zero in the C_O case. This may be attributed to the decreasing elementary cell dimensions in LuAG as compared to YAG, retaining less space for interstitials. Stronger bonding of Lu to oxygen as compared to Y, decreasing the probability to form oxygen vacancies may also contribute to the decrease in number of the mentioned defects. Herein, the Lu-O bond lengths are 2.29–2.41 Å in LuAG [17], whereas the Y-O bond length are 2.33–2.47 Å in YAG [18]. Under these conditions, carbon occupying aluminum vacancy C_{Al} becomes the most probable type of the isolated carbon-containing defects in LuAG:C. Note that Al-O distances are almost the same in LuAG (1.78–1.93 Å) [17] and YAG (1.78 – 1.94 Å) [18]. The obtained theoretical results confirm the

experimental data [19] on the depletion of YAG:C crystal surface with Al and oxygen, proving a high formation probability of C_O and C_{Al} .

5. Conclusions

We investigated the influence of carbon doping on stability of intrinsic defects in LuAG using first-principles calculations. Formation energies and charged states of carbon-containing complex defects are very similar in YAG:C and LuAG:C, whereas, by contrast to YAG:C, isolated charged C_O and C_i defects are not formed in LuAG:C.

Although it is barely possible to match defects of certain type with F-type related bands in the optical absorption spectra, one may assume that smaller amount of absorption bands in as-grown LuAG:C is related to the absence of charged C_O and C_i defects. Meanwhile, the same types of negatively charged carbon-related defects and no F-type bands in optical absorption spectra are observed in both materials annealed in oxidizing conditions.

Our further work should be focused on the simulation of energies and oxidation states of carbon-related defects in Ce-doped LuAG crystals grown under reducing CO-containing atmosphere, as well as undoped and Ce-doped perovskites ($YAlO_3$, $LuAlO_3$), which represent another class of efficient scintillators. $YAlO_3$, $LuAlO_3$ can be successfully grown under similar conditions in W crucibles. EPR study should be useful to get more information on the formation nature of carbon-related defects in rare-earth garnets and perovskites.

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